

Synthesis, spectral characterization, *in vitro* antimicrobial evaluation and DNA cleavage studies of few macrocyclic complexes

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Manuscript received 19 March 2008, revised 24 June 2009, accepted 3 July 2009

Abstract : Few macrocyclic complexes of the composition, [ML]X [M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, VO^{IV}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}; X = Cl₂/SO₄] have been designed and synthesized by the template condensation of malonic acid with 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane in ethanol medium. All the synthesized complexes were characterized by microanalytical data, magnetic susceptibility measurements, IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR, EPR and mass spectral techniques. They exhibit square-planar geometry except oxovanadium complex, which has square-pyramidal geometry. The electrolytic behaviour and monomeric nature of the complexes were confirmed from their conductance data and magnetic susceptibility. The X-band EPR spectra of Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and VO^{IV} complexes in DMSO at 300 and 77 K were recorded and their salient features are reported. The *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of the investigated compounds were evaluated against few microorganisms by well-diffusion technique. It was found that the metal complexes have higher activity than the standard. The cleavage activity of all the complexes was examined on pUC19 DNA using gel electrophoresis experiment in the presence of H₂O₂. From the data, it was found that all the complexes exhibit nuclease activity except vanadyl complex in the presence of H₂O₂.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, DNA cleavage study, square-planar geometry.

Introduction

Macrocyclic complexes have been widely studied in coordination chemistry as they selectively form strong polynuclear complexes with a variety of metal ions¹⁻⁵. The amide macrocyclic ligands are of interest because their metal complexes function similar to porphyrin analogues in catalysing organic oxidations⁶. Several groups⁷⁻⁹ are currently engaged in the synthesis of polyamide macrocycles. In most of the polyamide macrocyclic complexes, of the two potential donor atoms amide nitrogen and oxygen, only amide nitrogen is engaged in coordination and not the oxygen¹⁰. Mostly, the polyamide macrocycles formed on reduction with B₂H₆ or LiAlH₄ lead to the formation of their corresponding polyazamacrocycles¹¹, which may be used to further construct various macrocyclic systems. The formation of macrocyclic complexes mainly depends on the size of the internal cavity and rigidity of the macrocycle formed¹². The interaction of transition metal complexes with DNA is a significant area of research which has attracted much attention of both inorganic and biochemists, because biochemical studies have shown that they are related to the development

of new DNA reagents for biotechnology and medicine¹³. Keeping these facts in mind, it is proposed to design and synthesise few macrocyclic tetraamide transition metal complexes from a diacid and diamine with a view to study the biological applications of the complexes particularly the antimicrobial and DNA cleavage studies. The proposed structure of the macrocyclic complexes synthesized in the present work is given in Fig. 1.

Results and discussion

The macrocyclic complexes have been prepared by the condensation reaction of malonic acid with 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane and metal salts. They were found to be air stable and insoluble in water, but soluble in chloroform, acetonitrile, ethanol, DMSO and DMF. The high molar conductance values of these complexes indicate their electrolytic nature. The physical characterization, microanalytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The analytical data of the complexes correspond well with the general formula [ML]X [M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}; X = Cl₂/SO₄] The magnetic

M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II};
X = Cl₂/SO₄

Fig. 1. The proposed structure of the macrocyclic complexes.

susceptibility values of the complexes at room temperature are consistent with square-planar geometry around the central metal ion except oxovanadium complex which exhibits square-pyramidal geometry.

The UV-Vis spectrum of copper complex in EtOH solution displays a broad band at 18798 cm⁻¹ attributable to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} transition which strongly favours the square-planar geometry around the central metal ion^{14,15}.

The broadness of the band can be taken as an indication of distortion from the perfect square-planar geometry. The electronic absorption spectrum of the nickel complex shows two *d-d* bands at 16100 and 20100 cm⁻¹ which are assigned as ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} transitions¹⁶ indicating the square-planar geometry. The cobalt complex shows a *d-d* band at 16200 cm⁻¹ assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transition¹⁷. Electronic absorption spectrum of oxovanadium complex shows two *d-d* bands at ca. 11511 and 18063 cm⁻¹ which are assigned as ²B₂ → ²E and ²B₂ → ²B₁ transitions, respectively consistent with that of square-pyramidal geometry (Table 2)^{18,19}. These facts are also supported by their magnetic measurements.

A comparative study of the spectra of starting materials and complexes showed that the bands due to hydroxyl and primary amine groups disappear in the spectra of the complexes indicating the condensation of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane with malonic acid and formation of proposed macrocyclic frame-work. In addition, the appearance of four bands, mainly in the regions 1600–1618, 1529–1570, 1200–1276 and 625–665 cm⁻¹, due to amide moiety in-plane deformation vibrations²⁰, further suggests the formation of macrocyclic complexes. In the spectra of all the complexes a single peak is observed in

Table 1. Physical characterization, analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of the complexes

Compd.	Molecular formula	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				(Λ _M) (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
				M	C	H	N		
[CuL]Cl ₂	CuC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Brown	195	10.62 (10.66)	64.44 (64.47)	4.70 (4.70)	9.40 (9.40)	83	1.81
[CoL]Cl ₂	CoC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Pink	210	9.95 (9.97)	64.90 (64.98)	4.71 (4.73)	9.45 (9.47)	78	3.20
[NiL]Cl ₂	NiC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Green	195	9.90 (9.93)	65.00 (65.00)	4.72 (4.74)	9.44 (9.48)	72	-
[ZnL]Cl ₂	ZnC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Colourless	260	10.90 (10.94)	64.27 (64.27)	4.68 (4.68)	9.37 (9.37)	75	-
[MnL]Cl ₂	MnC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Dirty white	185	9.30 (9.35)	65.40 (65.42)	4.76 (4.77)	9.53 (9.54)	80	5.87
[VOL]SO ₄	VC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ SO ₉	Green	200	11.10 (11.17)	64.00 (64.11)	4.65 (4.67)	9.30 (9.34)	87	1.73
[CdL]Cl ₂	CdC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Colourless	213	17.41 (17.44)	59.56 (59.58)	4.32 (4.34)	8.50 (8.60)	90	-
[HgL]Cl ₂	HgC ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	Colourless	215	27.32 (27.38)	52.40 (52.41)	3.80 (3.82)	7.64 (7.64)	81	-

Table 2. Electronic absorption data of the complexes at 300 K

Complex	Absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Transition	Solvent	Geometry
[CuL]Cl ₂	36211	INCT	EtOH	Square planar
	26178	INCT		
	18790	² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}		
[CoL]Cl ₂	32807	INCT	EtOH	Square planar
	16978	INCT		
	16200	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}		
[NiL]Cl ₂	26241	INCT	EtOH	Square planar
	31501	INCT		
	16000	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}		
	20100	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}		
[VOL]SO ₄	33422	INCT	EtOH	Square planar
	30120	INCT		
	18063	² B ₂ → ² B ₁		
	11516	² B ₂ → ² E		

INCT - Intra-ligand charge transition.

the region 3150–3240 cm⁻¹ which is due to ν(NH) of amide group. The appearance of a new band in the region 410–435 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the ν(M–N) vibration which suggests that the amide nitrogen is coordinated to the metal atom. There is no band in the spectra of the complexes in the region 450–600 cm⁻¹ which clearly indicates that amide oxygen is not involved in the coordination with metal ion. In addition, the vanadyl complex displays a band at 974 cm⁻¹ assignable to V=O modes²¹.

The FAB mass spectra of the complexes were recorded and compared for their stoichiometric composition. The copper complex shows molecular ion peak at *m/z* 595 [Cu(C₃₂H₂₈N₄O₄)Cl₂]. The base peak observed at *m/z* 199 indicates the presence of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane moiety. The data confirm the stoichiometry of the metal complexes being [ML]X type. This is further supported by the mass spectra of the other complexes.

¹H NMR spectrum of the zinc complex was recorded in CDCl₃ solution. Proton resonance signals observed in the free 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane and malonic acid due to -NH₂ and -OH groups disappear completely in the spectrum of zinc complex indicating the condensation and formation of macrocyclic complexes. It is further confirmed by the appearance of a broad signal in the complex at δ 7.94–8.16 which is due to the amide (CO-NH) proton²². In the spectra of the complexes, a multiplet arising due to the methylene protons appears in the re-

gion δ 3.13–3.36²³, two multiplets at δ 7.6 due to phenyl group and singlets appear in the region δ 2.90–3.12 and 3.11–3.26 may be ascribed to methylene protons of malonic acid moiety. On the basis of the above discussion, it seems that the ligand acts as tetradentate chelating agent having four coordination sites.

The X-band EPR spectrum of the copper complex, recorded in DMSO at 300 and 77 K, is shown in the Fig. 2. The *g* tensor values of copper complex can be used to derive the ground state. In square-planar complexes, the unpaired electron lies in the *d*_{x²-y²} orbital giving ²B_{1g} as the ground state with *g*_∥ > *g*_⊥ > 2. From the observed values, it is clear that *A*_∥ = 160 > *A*_⊥ = 58, *g*_∥ = 2.37 > *g*_⊥ = 2.06 > 2 and the EPR parameters of the complexes coincide well with related systems which suggest that the complex has square-planar geometry and the system is axially symmetric²⁴. In the axial spectra, the *g*-values are related with exchange interaction coupling constant (*G*) by the expression, *G* = *g*_∥ - 2/*g*_⊥ - 2. According to Hathaway²⁵, if the value of *G* is larger than four, the exchange interaction is negligible because the local tetragonal axes are aligned parallel or slightly misaligned. If its value is less than four, the exchange interaction is considerable and the local tetragonal axes are misaligned. For present copper complex, the *G* value is 6.2, which suggests that the local tetragonal axis is aligned parallel or slightly misaligned and consistent with *d*_{x²-y²} ground state.

Fig. 2. The X-band ESR spectrum of the copper complex, recorded in DMSO at 300 K (a) and 77 K (b).

The in-plane σ -bonding covalency parameter (α^2) is found to be 0.80, indicating that the complex has covalent character. The out-of-plane π -bonding (γ^2) and in-plane π -bonding (β^2) parameters are also calculated. The observed β^2 (0.98) and γ^2 (0.673) values indicate that there is substantial interaction in the in-plane σ -bonding, whereas the in-plane π -bonding is completely ionic. This is also confirmed by the values of orbital reduction factors²⁶ (K_{\parallel} and K_{\perp}). In the case of pure π -bonding, $K_{\parallel} \sim K_{\perp}$ implies considerable in-plane π -bonding while for out-of-plane π -bonding $K_{\parallel} > K_{\perp}$. For the present copper complex, the observed order is K_{\parallel} (0.610) $<$ K_{\perp} (0.949) implying the presence of significant in-plane π -bonding.

The EPR spectrum of the vanadyl complex, recorded in DMSO solution at 300 and 77 K shows typical eight lines and sixteen line pattern respectively (Fig. 3). The isotropic EPR parameters $g_{\text{iso}} = 1.98$ and $A_{\text{iso}} = 104$ can be calculated from the position spacing of the resonance line from the room temperature solution spectrum of the complex. The spectrum is like a typical eight line pattern which shows that a single vanadium is present in the molecule i.e. it is a monomer. In the frozen solid state, the spectrum shows two types of resonance components, one set due to the parallel features and the other set due to the perpendicular features, which indicate axially symmetric anisotropy with well resolved sixteen line hyper-

fine splitting, characteristic of an interaction between the electron and vanadium nuclear spin. From the anisotropic spectrum, the anisotropic parameters were calculated. The observed order ($A_{\parallel} = 169 > A_{\perp} = 75$; $g_{\perp} = 1.99 > g_{\parallel} = 1.97$) indicates that the unpaired electron is present in the d_{xy} orbital with square-pyramidal geometry around the VO^{IV} chelate^{27,28}.

From the observed values of cobalt complex, it is clear that $A_{\parallel} = 119 > A_{\perp} = 68$; $g_{\perp} = 2.42 > g_{\parallel} = 2.04$. The EPR parameters of the complex coincide well with related systems which suggest that the complex has square-planar geometry. The EPR spectral study of Mn^{II} complex at room temperature shows only one isotropic signal centred at 2.145 g which once again suggests a four coordinated geometry for this complex.

Based on the spectral and analytical data, the proposed structure of the complexes (as given in Fig. 1) is confirmed.

Antimicrobial activity : For *in vitro* antimicrobial activity, the investigated compounds were tested against the bacteria *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizoctonia bataicola*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of the investigated complexes are summarized in Table 3. From the table, the observed MIC values indicate that most of the complexes have higher anti-microbial activity than the control. Such increased activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and the Tweedy's chelation theory²⁹. On chelation, the polarity of the metal ion will be reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with donor groups. Further, it increases the delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring and whole chelate ring and enhances the penetration of complexes into lipid membranes and blocking of the metal binding sites in the enzymes of microorganisms. These complexes also disturb the respiration process of the cell and thus block the synthesis of proteins, which restricts further growth of the organism³⁰.

DNA cleavage studies : The cleavage efficiency of the complexes compared to that of the control is due to their efficient DNA-binding ability. The metal complexes were able to convert super coiled DNA into open circular DNA. The general oxidative mechanisms proposed account of DNA cleavage by hydroxyl radicals via abstraction of a hydrogen atom from sugar units and predict the release

Fig. 3. The X-band ESR spectrum of the VO^{IV} complex at 300 K (a) and 77 K (b) in DMSO solution.

synthesized complexes in the presence of H_2O_2 as an oxidant. As can be seen from the results in Fig. 4, at very low concentration, all the complexes exhibit nuclease activity except vanadyl complex (due to its square-pyramidal geometry) in the presence of H_2O_2 . Control experiment using DNA alone (lane 8) does not show any significant cleavage of pUC19 DNA even on longer exposure time. From the observed results, it is concluded that the complexes, cobalt complex (lane 1), copper complex (lane 2), zinc complex (lane 3), cadmium complex (lane 4), nickel complex (lane 5) and mercury complex (lane 6) cleave DNA as compared to control DNA (lane 8) and vanadyl complex (lane 7) does not cleave DNA in the presence of H_2O_2 . Probably this may be due to the planarity of the complexes. Further, the presence of a smear in the gel diagram indicates the presence of radical cleavage³².

Experimental

The metal salts, malonic acid were purchased from E.

Table 3. Antimicrobial data of the investigated complexes
[Minimum inhibitory concentration $\times 10^{-2}$ M]

Compd.	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>R. bataicola</i>
[CuL]Cl ₂	4.8	4.0	4.1	3.8	5.2	5.0
[CoL]Cl ₂	4.2	4.1	4.2	4.6	3.8	4.0
[ZnL]Cl ₂	4.0	3.6	3.6	4.1	4.0	4.2
[NiL]Cl ₂	3.6	4.0	4.2	4.0	4.1	5.0
[VOL]SO ₄	3.3	3.7	5.1	4.2	4.4	3.8
[HgL]Cl ₂	3.5	5.1	4.2	4.0	4.5	4.3
[CdL]Cl ₂	3.0	4.1	4.6	4.1	4.6	3.7
[MnL]Cl ₂	4.1	3.8	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.4
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	3.2	2.3
Streptomycin	2.0	2.2	3.1	2.8	-	-

of specific residues arising from transformed sugars, depending on the position from which the hydrogen atom is removed³¹. The cleavage is inhibited by the free radical scavengers implying that hydroxyl radical or peroxy derivatives mediate the cleavage reaction. The reaction is modulated by a metallocomplexes bound hydroxyl radical or a peroxy species generated from the co-reactant H_2O_2 .

In the present study, the pUC19 DNA gel electrophoresis experiment was conducted at 35 °C using the

Merck and 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane was purchased from SDS fine chemicals. All the chemicals used were of AR grade. Anhydrous grade ethanol and DMSO were purified according to the standard procedures. The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents in each sample and FAB mass spectra of the samples were performed at Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. The ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds were recorded at Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai using tetramethylsilane as internal stan-

dard. The IR spectra of the samples were obtained as KBr discs in the range 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer. The UV-Vis spectra of the samples in the range 200–1100 nm in EtOH were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the paramagnetic complexes were recorded at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature as a corresponding glass in the X-band region on a Varian 112 at SAIF, IIT, Chennai, X-band spectrometer equipped with 100 kHz field modulation. Diphenyl picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used as the standard. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by employing the Gouy method at room temperature on powder sample of the complex. Copper sulphate was used as calibrant. The molar conductivity of the complexes was measured on a Systronic Model-304 digital direct reading conductivity meter using EtOH as solvent. Solutions of pUC19 DNA in 50 mM NaCl/50 mM tris-HCl (pH 7.2) gave a ratio of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm, A_{260}/A_{280} of ca. 1.8–1.9, indicating that the DNA was sufficiently free of protein contamination. The DNA concentration was determined by the UV absorbance at 260 nm after 1 : 100 dilutions. The molar absorbance coefficient was taken as 6600 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Stock solutions were kept at 4 °C and used after not more than 4 days. Doubly distilled H_2O was used to prepare the buffer.

Antimicrobial activity : The *in vitro* biological screen-

ing effects of the investigated compounds were tested against the bacteria such as *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* by the well diffusion method, using agar nutrient as the medium and streptomycin as the standard. The antifungal activities of the compounds were evaluated by the well diffusion method against the fungi viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizoctonia bataicola* cultured on potato dextrose agar as medium using fluconazole as the standard. The stock solution (10^{-2} M) was prepared by dissolving the compounds in EtOH and the solutions were serially diluted in order to find the MIC values. In a typical procedure, a well was made on the agar medium inoculated with microorganisms. The well was filled with the test solution using a micropipette and plate was incubated, 24 h for bacteria and 72 h for fungi at 35 °C. During this period, the test solution diffused and the growth of the inoculated microorganisms was affected. The inhibition zone was developed, at which the concentration was noted.

Gel electrophoresis : The gel electrophoresis experiments were performed by incubation at 35 °C for 2 h as follows : The samples containing pUC19 DNA 30 μM , 50 μM each complex, 50 μM H_2O_2 in 50 μM tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2) electrophoresed for 2 h at 50 V on 1% agarose gel using tris-acetic acid-EDTA buffer (pH 8.3). After electrophoresis, the gel was stained using 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ ethidiumbromide (EB) and photographed under UV light.

Preparation of complexes : An ethanolic solution (50

Fig. 4. Changes in the agarose gel electrophoretic pattern of pUC19 DNA induced by H_2O_2 and metal complexes :

Lanes left to right →

Lane 1 : DNA + Co^{II} complex

Lane 3 : DNA + Zn^{II} complex

Lane 5 : DNA + Ni^{II} complex

Lane 7 : DNA + VO^{IV} complex

Lane 2 : DNA + Cu^{II} complex

Lane 4 : DNA + Cd^{II} complex

Lane 6 : DNA + Hg^{II} complex

Lane 8 : DNA alone

mL) of MCl_2 (0.01 mol) was stirred with 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (0.02 mol) dissolved in ethanol. It was followed by the addition of ethanolic solution of malonic acid (0.02 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred continuously at room temperature for 2 h. The resultant solid product was filtered, washed several times with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his sincere thanks to the Principal, Head of the Department of Chemistry and the College Managing Board, VHNSN College, Virudhunagar for providing the research facilities.

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